

Multiscale in-situ 3D Imaging of Damage in a CMC Using Synchrotron and Laboratory X-Ray Microscopy

Hrishikesh Bale,

Carl Zeiss Microscopy Inc., Pleasanton CA

Robert O. Ritchie

Materials Sciences Division, University of California, Berkeley CA

D. B. Marshall and B. N. Cox

Teledyne Scientific Company, Thousand Oaks, CA

Overview

- Ceramic Matrix Composites
- In-situ synchrotron X-ray imaging
- Lab-based X-ray Microscopy

Carbon fibers composites and Ceramic Matrix Composites

Material Properties

- Specific strength vs T
- T vs Conductivity

Carbon fibers and Ceramic Matrix Composites Advantages

Over 20- 30 %
weight savings !

Reduced green house
emissions

Fuel Savings

Materials used in 787 body

- Fiberglass
- Aluminum
- Carbon laminate composite
- Carbon sandwich composite
- Aluminum/steel/titanium

Total materials used
By weight

By comparison, the 777 uses 12 percent composites and 50 percent aluminum.

Engine Efficiencies increase with increased operating T's

John Perepezko, Science, 2009 Vol. 326

MRS Bulletin • Volume 37 • Oct. 2012

Woven Ceramic Matrix Composite (CMC) In-situ multiscale non-destructive imaging under tensile loading

- CMC's a material of choice & an advanced structural material
- High Strength to weight ratio
- Woven CMC composite with SiC fiber bundles (tows).
- 3 layer angle interlocked composite coated with CVI-SiC

3 layer angle interlock CMC

5 mm

like natural materials,
these composites are
"robust through
complexity"

Image Credits : Teledyne Scientific Company, Thousand Oaks, CA

3D Hierarchical Materials

Virtual test method

Complex configurations and hierarchies mean complex damage mechanisms.
Std. Coupon tests are insufficient!

Virtual Design Pipeline

3D Hierarchical Materials

Virtual test method

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Std. Coupon tests are insufficient!

Woven 3-D SiC_f-SiC_m composite (Bale, et al, J Am Cer Soc. 2012); Cox et.al, Ann. Review of Mat., 2014

3D X-ray Imaging configurations

Synchrotron tomography

- **Projection** based architecture
- **Coherent parallel beam**
- **No Geometric magnification**
- *Magnification from objectives.*
- *Scintillator dependant*

Conventional MicroCT

- **Projection** based architecture
- **Resolution degrades substantially** as the sample moves away from the source

Lab X-ray Microscopy

- **Two-Stage Magnification** for Unprecedented Resolution and Contrast
- **High spatial resolution is maintained** as sample moves away from the source

Quantitative X-ray Tomography

Maire & Withers, *Int. Materials Review* (2014)

In situ ultra-high temperature testing

Tough behavior in reinforced ceramic matrix composites

Toughening mechanisms

- Distribution of damage over a broad are
- Multiple matrix cracks
- Interfacial debonding
- Frictional sliding resistance
- Fiber pullout

Micro-CT observations

Matrix crack-opening displacements in single tow SiC_f-SiC specimens at room temperature and 1750°C

Virtual Design: Direct Simulation of in situ results using Numerical Analysis

Virtual Design Pipeline

- virtual geometry generated from stochastics of real samples using micro-XCT
- numerical methods used to predict failure (Q. Yang, U. Maimi)

Laboratory X-ray Microscopy
IN-SITU TENSILE TESTING

Lab X-ray Microscopy

- **Two-Stage Magnification** for a high resolution and contrast
- **High spatial resolution is maintained using objectives** even if sample moves away from the source

Woven Ceramic Matrix Composite (CMC) In-situ multiscale non-destructive imaging under tensile loading

Sample Details

- 3 layer angle interlocked CMC
- Fibers – Carbon fibers
- Matrix – CVI –SiC
- 7 mm x 30 mm cut and notched using diamond saw
- Sample was mounted between brass tabs using epoxy and gripped in the tensile jaws

Woven CMC

Multiscale imaging under load

Switching to 20X objective 0.7 um/voxel

In-situ multiscale imaging

- Fast switching between objectives and RaAD facilitate imaging of ROIs during in-situ testing
- Switch between FFOV and high res.

Woven CMC

In-situ multiscale non-destructive imaging under tensile loading

- In-situ imaging of tensile loading at 4.4 μ m voxel resolution with incremental loads to failure at 1kN.

Woven CMC

4D Quantitative imaging

In-situ 4D imaging non-destructively captures the different strain states of a material as they evolve under loading conditions

- What happens between loaded state A and B?
- Can we predict upcoming hotspots of failure early on?
- Valuable data for validating predictive models of failure.

Woven CMC

4D Quantitative imaging from Lab XRM

10 um/voxel
resolution

4 um/voxel
resolution

Interior ultra hi-res tomography
0.7 $\mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$

Woven CMC 4D Quantitative imaging

Woven CMC

4D Quantitative imaging

Summary

- X-ray micro tomography provides the unique opportunity to probe into advanced materials non-destructively down to sub-micron resolutions.
- Rich three dimensional information pertaining to weave geometry, tow variations, defects, voids etc.
- 3D data can be directly used to produce virtual test specimens.
- In-situ testing under load reveals a vast amount of information related to damage initiation and propagation.
- Validate predictive models using real 3D/4D data.